

MODELS FOR EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE GOODS AND SERVICES MARKET IN THE REGIONAL INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Today, in the regional industry of our republic, the evaluation of the efficiency of the market of goods and services has a number of priorities as an important new direction. Based on the analysis of the scientific research works of the scientists who researched the market efficiency models for the purpose of these directions, various models were studied and based on them, a new conceptual model of increasing the market efficiency was developed. These measures are detailed in the article.

Keywords: Market, goods and services market, market model, market efficiency, conceptual model, market infrastructure, BKG matrix.

Introduction

It is known that today markets are focused on meeting the needs of the population as a form of implementation of economic relationships. As the most important priority in this regard, it is necessary to ensure their effectiveness and improve their efficiency. To this end, all economic reforms are deepening. To this day, the national economy has been reformed, effective measures have been taken to liberalize foreign trade, taxation and financial policy, support entrepreneurship and guarantee private property insecurity, in-depth recycling of agricultural products, and ensure the smooth development of regions. However, a strategy is needed to improve the more effective implementation of these tasks.

Today, an acceptable strategy has been developed and is considered to be the development of a new Uzbekistan development strategy as its important task, with the development of a new U.S. development strategy for 2022-2026. According to the strategy, 130 modern markets and commercial complexes, as well as 65 large and 5,000 small service facilities for road infrastructure development, are set to be established through the development of commercial and road services in the regions of the country. These tasks require the

development of priority directions for improving and evaluating market efficiency in the region.

Literature analysis

The efficiency of the goods and services market is regarded as an important indicator. Various scientists have carried out research on market efficiency assessment. They approached differently and studied market efficiency based on different models.

The model is needed for market efficiency and its enhancement. A model is a form of complex or system perception or diagramming. A model is included in the set of internal consistent statements on wholesale advertising, sales or pricing. Any consistent set of mathematical statements about some aspects of the market can be seen as a model.

It is often advantageous to model the demand for a brand based on market share rather than an absolute sale. It affects the likelihood of switching between aggregated numbers of normal models of market share and brands hidden away.

There are two main reasons why interactive marketing models go beyond the experimental stage. Calculating decisions is a set of model-based procedures for processing decisions and data to help the manager make decisions.

Models are evaluated by theoretical criteria and management criteria. Based on these criteria, three models are useful. The test market concludes with discussion of future areas of research in the field of models.

Indeed, the only choice available will be between conscious models and subconscious models and models that have been verified and superficially verified or not.

The model is highly malfunctioning, preventing the acquisition of accurate solutions or analytical stability analysis.

The business model is a way of creating and acquiring value within the market network of business developers, suppliers and consumers. Businessmodeli concept is related to business strategy (business model design process) and business operations (the introduction of a company business model into organizational structures and systems).

An important problem in emerging business models is the development of business and financing models that promote their rapid growth.

There are three key requirements for Luke's criticism to be relevant: awareness of the change of economic agents, the ability to encourage them to change their behavior, and the ability to change their behavior. This means that the requirements are more suited to long-term models.

From these analyses, we have seen that models are necessary to evaluate market effectiveness.

Research Methodology

The study used methods such as observation, comparative analysis, synthesis, content analysis, systematic approach, modeling, and BCG (Boston consulting grouping).

Results and discussion

The modern interpretation of the market is the marketing sector, and its practical outcome will directly depend on the market and its effective development as a study of it. Marketing practices are performed to effectively maintain the market and reform its content. To do this, effective market analysis should be carried out and this analysis should be analyzed at a regional, national and international level.

In the process of developing international marketing, the following concepts have emerged in terms of market analysis:

- the concept of an expanded national market;
- the concept of a multinational market;
- the concept of a global market.

The enlarged national market within these is the original market concept. The primary market is the national market, the secondary is the foreign market, the national market is viewed as an additional "program" that is effective. In addition, the strategy of expanding the national market can bring benefits.

Markets influenced the development of countries, and markets of such a form were formed. A country with an emerging market is a period of transition from a mustabid state to a free market-oriented economy.

Market efficiency refers to the level of market prices reflecting all available, relevant information. Markets are generally considered to be either efficient or ineffective compared to each of the three different levels. There are various following levels of efficacy:

- a form of strong efficiency;
- semi-strong form of efficiency;
- weak form of productivity.

The effectiveness of the levels of productivity is determined by efficiency and reflects the working aspects of the market.

Efficiency is understood to be a framework of economic relationships between society, government, owner, enterprise, workforce, and entities in

exchange for the efficient use of all available resources and the transparency of expenses, regardless of their ownership.

Based on economic relationships, the development of regional regions is measured by a benchmark of efficiency.

When it comes to the criterion for efficiency, it is understood that the result achieved is a unit of measure measured by the ratio of the resources used to achieve it or the costs incurred.

Market efficiency is information efficiency. That is, market efficiency is a market that reflects certain information about the situation in the market. Prices in such a market are fair, that is, their change is random, and they instantly and fully reflect information that has a positive and negative effect.

As the performance of the market is determined by prices, it affects its market performance. There are also a number of critical theoretical and practical considerations against the hypothesis of market performance. For example, this is illustrated by the Paradox of Grossman-Stiglitz. On the basis of it, the internal logical problem is that the market, even theoretically, cannot be fully efficient in the long run. This is due to the fact that active participants must work to achieve market performance and they will make the market effective with their deals.

The European Commission uses the QUEST model to carry out market analysis. QUEST is a global macroeconomic model developed for macroeconomic policy analysis and research [6]. That said, the QUEST, which is a member of the new Keynesian dynamic stochastic general balance models class, has strict microeconomic foundations rooted in profit-optimization and includes frictions in the commodities, labor and financial markets.

The model focuses on assessing normal sales performance. Evaluating the effectiveness of the goods and services market may be characteristic of a common model for developing market infrastructure management. All infrastructure management markets are consistently implemented at the following stages of development:

- an undeveloped market;
- an emerging market;
- a developed market;
- advanced market.

One modern critic of the Porter concept, Larry Downs, points out that Porter's models are not life-appropriate. At the same time, Downs defines the following three new strengths of market competition:

- digitization;
- globalization;
- abolition of regulation.

Accordingly, the emergence of these competitive forces requires the development of new models and tools for managing competitiveness.

Market infrastructure is an important element for market performance assessment models. Market infrastructure is a system of institutions that serve to establish market relations and operate by a margin. It includes warehouse farms, transportation, communications services companies, institutions that serve the treatment of goods and services, financial and credit relationships, and institutions that serve the social sector.

Market infrastructure will be unique to each region. Therefore, it is a concept that is unique to each region in the context of a regional market.

Depending on the territory, the regional market or mesomarket is divided into the domestic regional market:

- a micromarket representing the type of market in the city or district of the province;
- minimarket - urban area market or settlements, settlements, local market
- market for a particular area;
- nanobozor - market relations sell and buy at a specific location or point of the process.

Models based on all structures are used to evaluate the effectiveness of the goods and services market.

There are the following 10 popular marketing models that can be used to predict customer behavior, company growth, and revenue expectations:

- SWOT and TOWS analysis. SWOT and TOWS are both shortcuts for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. While both use the same basic ideas in their analysis, TOWS puts a strain on the external environment, while SWOT focuses on the internal environment. These models help to visualize strategic options and direct the strengths and minimize weaknesses to avoid threats and maximize opportunities.

- 7Ps marketing mix. 7P in the marketing mix refers to product, price, niche, advertising, people, process, and physical proof. Marketing mix is a common marketing model that helps organize the stages of business strategy from concept to evaluation. Using a 7Ps deployment, it is possible to analyze every aspect of the company to optimize the strategy and identify ways to achieve goals.

- Porter's five forces. It is competitive competition, supplier strength, customer strength, replacement threat and new entry threat. This model is unique, and it measures profitability by focusing less on the product or audience and more on external influences and competition. Using this analytics can be a simple but powerful way to make businesses understand competitiveness.

- The STP marketing model (segmentation, target determination, positioning) is the basis for simplifying the market segmentation process. STP refers to segmentation, purpose and location. It is a popular model that leverages the top-down approach by focusing on how the company addresses customers. Marketing is much more effective by dividing the market into groups, targeting the right groups, and placing products and services in those groups.

- AIDA. This marketing model is entirely customer-focused and represents insight, interest, desire, and action. These are the four stages in which the customer goes through the process of buying a service or product. This model appeals to the customer's choice to make return purchases and build a loyalty to the brand. This model is unique, it recognizes the impact of social media on buyer and seller relationships and incorporates it into a sales strategy. As a result, other customers can share material and create online communities that affect customer behaviour.

- Growth share matrix. The growth share matrix uses four quadrants to help businesses decide how to prioritise their various businesses. In this marketing model, the Y-axis shows top-of-bottom growth and the X-axis shows higher and lower market shares. The matrix represents each of the four quadrants with such signs as "stars", "cows", "question marks" and "pets".

- Life cycle of the product. The life cycle model of a product can help you develop new products, refine existing products and figure out if it's time to stop the product. It consists of four stages and manages marketing activities such as input, growth, maturity and decline during product production: Based on the aforementioned approaches, a model is needed to improve market efficiency in Khmer Rouge. It is divided into groups, such as a system for ensuring market efficiency and increasing market efficiency in the form of a system. Regional policy should also be developed to ensure it.

- SOSTAC. The SOSTAC model is a versatile planning model that is used to build marketing strategies. That is, it is the situation, goals, strategy, tactics, action and control. This can be a suitable tool to review the process and identify its weaknesses. Each step in it represents an important part of the development process: identifying current conditions, defining goals, developing a strategy,

describing how it plans to implement the strategy, developing a plan, and reviewing these steps to make sure the goals are achieved.

- Ansoff matrix. Also known as product or market expansion network, the Ansoff Matrix is a size 2x2 network that sets out four strategies that can be used to grow a business and analyze potential risks. The safest of the four options is market access, the lower left quadrant. Entering the market happens when you expand the sales of an existing product to the existing market. According to ansoff matrix, the most dangerous option is the top right quadrant: diversification. Diversification means introducing an untested product to the new market.

- McKinsey 7-S model. The McKinsey 7-S model defines seven key elements (strategy, structure, systems, styles, employees, qualifications, and shared values) that business must work in harmony to be successful. The common scope of values in the center connects other circles to show that each of the elements is important for ensuring organizational success and flexibility.

The aforementioned suitable models can serve to improve market efficiency directly. Evaluation of the effectiveness of regional policy on consumer market development can be carried out in the following key areas:

- an increase in organizations that sell goods to the population and provide paid services;
- ensuring the territorial availability of services and improving trade services;
- increase the turnover and volume of paid services;
- population growth and living standards;
- additional revenues to the republic's budget.

These priority areas prohibit the development of a model for the region of Khorezm region aimed at improving the efficiency of the goods and services market in order to strengthen the market's impact on gross domestic product. It includes such elements as increasing economic activity, improving the use of services, selecting workforce markets, and creating single infrastructure networks.

Conceptual model directions, in turn, can be manifested in the form of a clearly defined system of measures.

Conclusions

To improve the efficiency of the market for goods and services in the region, mechanisms for shaping regional policies and improving its efficiency are needed. These processes are unique to the BKG matrix model for market

efficiency and require a model aimed at implementing a service system in the goods and services market. It is intended to develop a conceptual model aimed at improving market efficiency as a practical nataj of this. These areas also serve as priority directions for assessing the effectiveness of the goods and services market for the region of Khorezm region.

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